

Value addition to Rasgulla (a traditional Indian Sweet) through Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) leaf extract

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Abstract

The proximate analysis and mineral composition were studied in tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) collected from Singur region of Hooghly district in West Bengal (India). The extract of the leaf was mixed with channa (a milk product) to prepare rasgulla, a famous traditional Indian sweet. The composition of the prepared rasgulla was studied and compared with the control (where the tulsi leaf extract was not mixed). Significant variation in composition was observed between control and experimental rasgullas. Our first order analysis exhibits a better/upgraded performance in terms of nutritional value of rasgulla, which may provide a wide avenue for the replication of such non-conventional sweet industry.

Keywords: Nutritional Value, Rasgulla, Singur, Sweet Industry, Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*).

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1. Introduction

Ocimum sanctum, commonly known as Holy Basil, belongs to *Lamiaceae* family (Fig. 1). The plant is used in Indian sub-continent since long time back to treat various types of human diseases (Pattanayak *et al.*, 2010; Saharkhiz *et al.*, 2015). The leaf is taken in many forms such as in herbal tea, dried powder, fresh leaf mixed with honey *etc.* to protect against cough and cold. It has also been documented that tulsi may be a COX-2 inhibitor like several model pain killers due to its significant amount of eugenol (Rao *et al.*, 2013, Pattanayak *et al.*, 2010; Gaber *et al.*, 2015). The plant contains several bioactive compounds (Devendran and Balasubramanian, 2010; Triveni Kumar *et al.*, 2013). Recent studies have shown the presence

of several chemicals of pharmaceutical importance in this species (Rao *et al.*, 2013, Pattanayak *et al.*, 2010; Gupta *et al.*, 2002). Considering the meritorious background of the species, the present pilot scale experiment was conducted by the researchers and sweet makers of Satyanarayan Mistanna Bhandar, Singur, Hooghly district, West Bengal (India) to prepare special type of rasgulla by mixing formulated proportion of tulsi leaf extract in place of water in sugar syrup (Fig 1). The primary vision of this study is to upgrade the quality of the sweet in terms of nutritional value and orient the local level traditional track of sweet making through the lane of pharmaceutical science.

Figure 1. Preparation of rasgulla from tulsi extract at Satyanarayan Mistanna Bhandar, Singur, Hooghly district, West Bengal (India).

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Analysis of *Ocimum sanctum* (tulsi) leaf

Fresh leaves of tulsi were collected from Singur region (22°81'50" N; 88°23'45" E) of Hooghly district in West Bengal from different patches. The dried leaf samples were grinded by mortal pastel and protein content was measured by Lowry's method using spectrophotometer as per the standard procedure (Lowry *et al.*, 1951). The total carbohydrate content was estimated by phenol sulphuric acid method using D-Glucose as standard (Dubois *et al.*, 1956). The total fat in the leaf sample was estimated by Soxhelt method using petroleum ether (80°C) as per the procedure (AOAC, 2000). The ascorbic acid of leaf sample was quantified as per the

standard protocol (Zvaigzne *et al.*, 2009; Nielsen, 1998) and expressed in mg/100 gm. Minerals like Ca, K and Mg were analysed as per the standard method of flame photometry.

2.2. Preparation of *Ocimum sanctum* leaf extract

The collected tulsi leaves were shade dried and powdered. The dried leaf dusts were soaked overnight in sterilized water and filtered through fine loin cloth. The filtrate was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 20 minutes using a REMI cold centrifuge. The supernatant, thus obtained, was filtered through loin cloth and the collected filtrate was preserved at -20°C in clean Tarson bottles.

2.3. Preparation of rasgulla with tulsi extract

Rasgulla is prepared from soft and freshly made channa. Cow milk is preferred for the production of rasgulla because it gives soft, spongy and juicy product.

For rasgulla production, channa is kneaded into smooth paste and then small balls of about 15-20 mm diameter and 10-15 grams in weight are made. The surface of balls should be smooth and free from any cracks. One kg of channa yields about 40-60 rasgullas (depending on the size of the rasgulla). Rasgulla balls are cooked in sugar syrup having 50-60 percent sugar concentration for about 15-20 minutes. During cooking, a small

amount of water is continuously added to maintain sugar concentration. This makes up for the loss of water due to evaporation. About 10 percent of cooking solution is replaced by fresh one, every time it is reused to cook another batch of rasgulla. After cooking rasgulla, balls are soaked in 40-45 percent sugar syrup for about 1-23 hours. Our specially formulated rasgulla replaced the water of sugar syrup with *O. sanctum* leaf extract and mixed with equivalent proportion of sugar as that of normal (control). The entire marketing of this formulated rasgulla was done by Satyanarayan Mistanna Bhandar, Singur, Hooghly district, West Bengal (India) (Fig 2).

Figure 2. Sticker and signboard (both in English and local language-Bengali) for marketing tulsi extract based rasgulla.

Figure 3. View of control (without tulsi extract) rasgulla and experimental (with tulsi extract).

2.4. Analysis of rasgulla (a comparative analysis of control and experimental samples)

The success of any experimental approach is monitored on the basis of a comparative study between control and experimental samples (Fig 3) in terms of few parameters (variables)

that are relevant indicators of human health. In the present programme, we have used the values of protein, carbohydrate, fat, ascorbic acid, Ca, K and Mg as indicators of comparative study. These indicators (compounds/elements) are intricately related to human health.

3. Results

Figure 4. Composition of *O. sanctum* leaf; Units of protein, carbohydrate and fat are in percentage; for ascorbic acid the unit is mg/100 gm and for Ca, K and Mg, the units are mg/100g dry matter.

Figure 5. Comparative study of nutritional value between control (without tulsi extract) and experimental (with tulsi extract) rasgullas.

Fig. 4 presents the composition of *O. sanctum* leaf.

Fig. 5 represents a comparative picture of control and experimental samples, which clearly depicts the improvement of the experimental rasgulla (prepared from tulsi extract), from the nutritional point of view.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Rasgulla is undoubtedly the most popular traditional Indian milk sweet prepared from channa. The soft ball of channa soaked in sugar syrup delights the taste buds of sweet lovers. However to many customers, this sweet ball is a cause of concern as the sweet sugar is intricately related with diabetes. Hence, the diabetic patients usually avoid the consumption of this delicious sweet. There are various types of rasgulla sold in the market. This includes ordinary sugar mixed with rasgulla, spongy rasgulla even diabetic rasgulla. Spongy rasgulla differs in terms of taste, texture body and succulent as compared to ordinary rasgulla. The diabetic rasgulla is prepared by replacing sucrose with low calorie sweeteners or alcoholic sugar such as sorbitol to cater the need of the people suffering from diabetes to health conscious consumers. In this pilot programme, we have introduced *O. sanctum* leaf extract with the aim to introduce the medicinal value of the species to the consumer through mouth watering rasgulla. We observe that there is an increase of 48.68 % protein in our formulated rasgulla compared to control samples. Interestingly the fat and sucrose have decreased by 32.74 % and 9.43 % respectively. Also the minerals like Ca and K have increased. The ascorbic acid has also increased in the experimental rasgulla which strongly confirms the role of this formulated sweet to fight against cough and cold. It can be concluded from the current work that the consumption of this specially formulated rasgulla from *O. sanctum* leaf extract has the capability to provide the protection against several diseases preferably cough and cold, which is very common amongst the population of the tropical countries. We expect that the pharmaceutical benefits of tulsi (Annexure) can be introduced in human system through

this effort of preparing rasgulla from the leaf extract of the species, provided a back-up nursery is maintained for a regular flow of this unique medicinal raw material.

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Annexure

1. With high levels of beta-carotene, vitamin A, cryptoxanthin, lutein and zeaxanthin in tulusi, the plant parts act as protective scavengers against oxygen-derived free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS), thereby preventing premature aging and various diseases. The high level of vitamin C also helps to fight against cough and cold.
2. Tulsi is rich in zeaxanthin. Zeaxanthin, a yellow flavonoid carotenoid compound, helps in filtering harmful UV rays by reaching the retina, thereby protecting against age related muscular degeneration (ARMD), particularly in elderly people.
3. Tulsi contains exceptionally high amounts of vitamin A, which is essential for good vision due to its antioxidant properties. Besides, it is also necessary for maintaining a healthy mucus membrane and skin.
4. Tulsi contains significant amounts of vitamin K, which plays an important role in strengthening bones and assisting the mineralization process of the bones.
5. Potassium, manganese, copper and magnesium are vital for the proper functioning of the body. While potassium is required for controlling heart rate and blood pressure, manganese is important for the antioxidant enzyme superoxide dismutase. Tulsi has all these compounds in considerable level and hence, should form a part of a healthy diet.
6. Tulsi is a good source of volatile oils, like eugenol, cineole, estragole, limonene, linalool, myrcene, sabinene and others, which have strong anti-bacterial properties. These oils combine to fight against many bacterial infections, such as enterococcus, staphylococcus etc.
7. With anti-inflammatory effects, tulsi is recommended to people suffering from arthritis. Basil oil, in particular, contains eugenol, a substance that blocks the activity of an enzyme in the body called cyclo-oxygenase which causes swelling.
8. Magnesium, present in considerable quantity in tulsi, relaxes the muscles and blood vessels, thereby improving blood flow and reducing the risk of irregular heart rhythm of heart muscles and blood vessels.
9. Tulsi oil makes unique skin and hair moisturizer, as it enhances the luster and shine of dull looking skin and hair. Tulsi is widely used for curing skin problems, such as acne and psoriasis.
10. Constipation, stomach cramps, indigestion and flatulence can be treated by consuming tulsi tea. As such, it provides immediate relief from gas in the stomach and intestines.
11. The essential oil of tulsi acts as an anti-vomiting agent in motion sickness and various other vomiting cases. Besides, it is highly recommended in effectively curing cold, influenza, whooping cough, asthma, bronchitis and sinus infections.

12. For treating stress-related problems like migraines and depression, tulsi oil finds a significant place in aromatherapy due to its calming effects and promotion of mental strength and clarity.

13. Tulsi, when consumed in the form of herbal tea, helps in alleviating the symptoms of urinary infections, colics, anorexia, gastric ulcers and diarrhoea.

14. Tulsi is widely used in ayurvedic medicines for curing a variety of common ailments, such as diabetes, respiratory disorders, impotence, allergies, and infertility.

15. With a powerful compound called cinnamamic acid present, tulsi has been proved to stimulate circulation, stabilize blood sugar and improve respiration.

16. Effective treatment of skin rashes, eczema, wounds and insect bites constitute other valuable health benefits of tulsi.